

Appendix of Adversarially Robust Neural Lyapunov Control

A Controller Learning for Discrete-Time Control

We consider a discrete-time dynamical system sampled from a continuous-time dynamical system with fixed time interval Δt :

$$x'_t = x_{t+\Delta t} = x_t + \dot{x}\Delta t = f(x_t, a_t^\mu, a_t^\nu), \quad (\text{A-1})$$

where $a_t^\mu \in \mathcal{A}$ and $a_t^\nu \in \mathcal{A}_{adv}$ are the controller's action and adversary's action at time $t \in \mathbb{N}$ following their policies π_μ and π_ν , respectively; and x'_t is the state at time $t + \Delta t$ (i.e., at the next sampling step).

Theorem A-1 (Lyapunov stability theorem for discrete-time dynamical systems). *For a discrete-time dynamical system in Eq. (A-1), if there exists a continuous function $V: \mathcal{X} \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ such that*

$$V(0) = 0; \text{ and } V(x) > 0, \forall x \in \mathcal{X} - \{0\}; \text{ and } V(x') - V(x) < 0; \quad (\text{A-2})$$

then the system is asymptotically stable at $x = 0$, where V is called a Lyapunov function.

For the discrete-time dynamical system, we focus on the difference of the Lyapunov function instead of the time derivative in the continuous-time case. To satisfy the Lyapunov stability theorem, we require that: *i*) the value of $V(0)$ is zero; *ii*) the value of $V(x)$ is positive; and *iii*) the value of the difference $V(x') - V(x)$ is negative.

Definition A-1 (Discrete-time perturbed Lyapunov risk for controller). We consider a candidate Lyapunov function V_θ parameterized by θ for discrete-time dynamical system in Eq. (A-1). In the presence of an adversary policy π_ν parameterized by θ_ν , the discrete-time perturbed Lyapunov risk for the controller μ is defined by:

$$L_\rho(\theta, \theta^\mu, \theta^\nu) = \mathbb{E}_{x \sim \rho(\mathcal{X})} \left(\max(-V_\theta(x), 0) + \max(0, V_\theta(x') - V_\theta(x)) + V_\theta^2(0) \right), \quad (\text{A-3})$$

where $\rho(\mathcal{X})$ is the state distribution.

In practice, we use the following empirically perturbed Lyapunov risk, which is an unbiased estimator of Eq. (A-3):

$$L_{n,\rho}(\theta, \theta^\mu, \theta^\nu) = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{i=1}^N \left(\max(-V_\theta(x_i), 0) + \max(0, V_\theta(x'_i) - V_\theta(x_i)) + V_\theta^2(0) \right). \quad (\text{A-4})$$

We use the negations of the Lyapunov conditions in Lyapunov stability theorem to define the counter-examples, which means that if the value of $V_\theta(x)$ is non-positive or the value of the difference $V_\theta(x') - V_\theta(x)$ is non-negative, then the state x is considered as a counter-example. Therefore, the criterion for discrete-time dynamical systems can be set as follows:

$$\Omega(x) = V_\theta(x) \leq 0 \vee V_\theta(x') - V_\theta(x) \geq 0, \forall x \in \mathcal{X} - \{0\}. \quad (\text{A-5})$$

B ARNLC for Known System Dynamics

We summarize the ARNLC for known system dynamics f in Algorithm A-1 of this Appendix. Its difference from ARNLC for unknown system dynamics lies in that there is no need to learn an environment model. This algorithm follows the same alternating procedure as described in Section 4.3 in the main text to train the controller's and the adversary's policies.

Algorithm A-1 Adversarially robust neural Lyapunov control for known system dynamics

Input: known dynamical system f and state space \mathcal{X} **Output:** learned policies π_μ and π_ν

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1: Initialize:  $\theta^\mu$  for controller  $\mu$ ,  $\theta^\nu$  for adversary  $\nu$ ,  $\theta$  for Lyapunov function  $V_\theta$ , control interval  $\Delta t$ 
2: for  $i = 1, 2, \dots, N_{iter}$  do
3:   Randomly sample  $M_1$  states  $\mathcal{S} = \{x_k\}_{k=1}^{M_1}$  from state space  $\mathcal{X}$ 
4:   for  $j_\mu = 1, 2, \dots, N_\mu$  do ▷ train controller
5:      $a_k^\mu = \pi_\mu(x_k)$ ,  $a_k^\nu = \pi_\nu(x_k)$  and  $x'_k = f(x_k, a_k^\mu, a_k^\nu)$  on  $\{x_k\}_{k=1}^{M_2}$  sampled from  $\mathcal{S}$ 
6:      $\pi_\mu, V_\theta \leftarrow \min_{\theta, \theta^\mu} L_\rho(\theta, \theta^\mu, \theta^\nu)$  on  $\{x_k, a_k^\mu, a_k^\nu, x'_k\}_{k=1}^{M_2}$  ▷ use SGD to update
7:     Find counter-example set  $\Omega$  of size  $M_3$  following criterion in Eq. (A-5) and  $\mathcal{S} \leftarrow \mathcal{S} \cup \Omega$ 
8:   end for
9:   for  $j_\nu = 1, 2, \dots, N_\nu$  do ▷ train adversary
10:     $\{x_h, a_h^\mu, a_h^\nu, r_h\}_{h=1}^{N_{traj}} \leftarrow \text{generate}(f, \pi_\mu, \pi_\nu)$ 
11:     $\pi_\nu \leftarrow \text{policyOptimize}(\{x_h, a_h^\mu, a_h^\nu, r_h\}_{h=1}^{N_{traj}}, \pi_\nu)$ 
12:   end for
13: end for
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Table A-1: Lyapunov function and controller policy specific settings

Task	Network Architecture		Training Iterations	Learning Rate	Batch Size
	Lyapunov Function	Controller Policy			
Pendulum	2-6-1	2-1	200		
Cart Pole	4-64-64-1	4-64-64-1	20	0.01	512
Car Trajectory Tracking	2-64-1	2-1	12		
2-link Pendulum	4-6-1	4-64-2	6		
Inverted Pendulum	4-64-64-1	4-64-64-1	40		

Table A-2: Adversary hyperparameters

Parameter	Value
Optimizer	Adam
Learning rate for actor policy network	3×10^{-4}
Learning rate for critic network	1×10^{-3}
Discount (γ)	0.99
Clipping ratio (ϵ)	0.2
Number of hidden layers (all tasks)	2
Number of hidden units per layer	64
Nonlinearity	tanh

C Details of Experimental Settings

The network architectures for Lyapunov function and controller policy are tuned for each task and are summarized in Table A-1. The detailed hyperparameters for adversary policy training are summarized in Table A-2. The environment specific parameters are summarized in Table A-3.

C.1 System Dynamics

Pendulum. The system is shown in Fig. A-1 and the system dynamics can be described as

$$\ddot{\theta} = \frac{mgl \sin(\theta) + u - b\dot{\theta}}{ml^2}, \quad (\text{A-6})$$

where $m = 0.15$, $g = 9.81$, $b = 0.1$ and $l = 0.5$.

Table A-3: Environment specific parameters

Task	State Space	Adversary Reward
Pendulum	$ \varphi \leq 6, \dot{\varphi} \leq 6$	φ^2
Cart Pole	$ x \leq 1, \dot{x} \leq 1, \varphi \leq 0.2, \dot{\varphi} \leq 1$	-1 if $ \varphi < 0.2$
Car Trajectory Tracking	$ x_e \leq 0.5, \varphi_e \leq 0.5$	$ x_e + \varphi_e $
2-link Pendulum	$ \varphi_1 \leq 0.8, \dot{\varphi}_1 \leq 0.8, \varphi_2 \leq 0.8, \dot{\varphi}_2 \leq 0.8$	$ \varphi_1 + \varphi_2 $
Inverted Pendulum	$ x \leq 1, \dot{x} \leq 1, \varphi \leq 0.2, \dot{\varphi} \leq 1$	-1 if $ \varphi < 0.2$

Figure A-1: Schematic diagram of the Pendulum task.

The adversary reward in this environment is set as the square of the normalized angle between the pendulum and the goal state. The actions of the adversary are set to adding an external force to the pendulum, changing the acceleration of gravity in the environment, changing the length of the pendulum, changing the coefficient of friction, and changing the mass of the ball, respectively.

Cart Pole. The system is shown in Fig. A-2 and the system dynamics can be described as

$$\ddot{\theta} = \frac{g \sin \theta + \cos \theta \left(\frac{-u - m_p l \dot{\theta}^2 \sin \theta}{m_c + m_p} \right)}{l \left(\frac{4}{3} - \frac{m_p \cos^2 \theta}{m_c + m_p} \right)}, \quad (\text{A-7})$$

$$\ddot{x} = \frac{u + m_p l (\dot{\theta}^2 \sin \theta - \ddot{\theta} \cos \theta)}{m_c + m_p},$$

where $g = 9.8, m_c = 1.0, m_p = 0.1, l = 0.5$.

Figure A-2: Schematic diagram of the Cart Pole task.

If the angle between the pendulum and the vertical direction is less than 0.2, the adversary gets reward -1. The actions of the adversary are set to adding an external force to the cart, changing the acceleration of gravity in the environment, changing the length of the pendulum, changing the mass of the cart, and changing the mass of the ball, respectively.

Car Trajectory Tracking. The system is shown in Fig. A-3 and the system dynamics can be

described as

$$\begin{aligned}\dot{s} &= \frac{v \cos(\theta_e)}{1 - \dot{d}_e \kappa(s)}, \\ \dot{d}_e &= v \sin(\theta_e), \\ \dot{\theta}_e &= \frac{v \tan(u)}{L} - \frac{v \kappa(s) \cos(\theta_e)}{1 - \dot{d}_e \kappa(s)},\end{aligned}\tag{A-8}$$

where $v = 6$, $l = 1$.

Figure A-3: Schematic diagram of the Car Trajectory Tracking task.

The adversary reward in this environment is set as the sum of the absolute value of the distance error and the absolute value of the normalized angle error. The actions of the adversary are set to adding an external force to the pendulum, changing the velocity of the car, and changing the radius of the target path, respectively.

2-link Pendulum. The system is shown in Fig. A-4 and the system dynamics can be described as

$$\begin{aligned}\ddot{\theta}_1 &= \frac{a_{22}[u_1 + a_{12}\dot{\theta}_2^2 \sin(\theta_2 - \theta_1) + b_1 \sin \theta_1] - a_{12} \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1)[u_2 + a_{21}\dot{\theta}_1^2 \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + b_2 \sin \theta_2]}{a_{11}a_{22} - a_{12}a_{21} \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1)}, \\ \ddot{\theta}_2 &= \frac{a_{21} \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2)[u_1 + a_{12}\dot{\theta}_2^2 \sin(\theta_2 - \theta_1) + b_1 \sin \theta_1] - a_{11}[u_2 + a_{21}\dot{\theta}_1^2 \sin(\theta_1 - \theta_2) + b_2 \sin \theta_2]}{a_{12}a_{21} \cos(\theta_2 - \theta_1) \cos(\theta_1 - \theta_2) - a_{11}a_{22}},\end{aligned}\tag{A-9}$$

where

$$\begin{aligned}a_{11} &= I_1 + m_1 l_{c1}^2 + l_1^2 m_2, \\ a_{12} &= a_{21} = m_2 l_1 l_{c2}, \\ a_{22} &= I_2 + m_2 l_{c2}^2, \\ b_1 &= (m_1 l_{c1} + l_1 m_2)g, \\ b_2 &= (m_2 l_{c2})g,\end{aligned}\tag{A-10}$$

and $I_1 = I_2 = 1$, $m_1 = m_2 = 1$, $l_1 = l_2 = 1$, $l_{c1} = l_{c2} = 0.5$, $g = 9.8$.

Figure A-4: Schematic diagram of the 2-link Pendulum task.

The adversary reward in this environment is set as the sum of the normalized angles between the two pendulums and the goal state. The actions of the adversary are set to adding two external forces to the pendulum, changing the length of the first pendulum, and changing the position of the center of

mass of the first pendulum, respectively.

Inverted Pendulum. This task is provided by MuJoCo, where the goal is to control a cart (attached to a pendulum) to balance the whole system and keep the pendulum upright, as shown in Fig. A-5. Since the system dynamics of Inverted Pendulum are unknown, it is impossible to generate perturbations on concrete physical parameters at each control step. Therefore, we only conduct the generalization test in the entire perturbation space for this task. If the angle between the pendulum and the vertical direction is less than 0.2, the adversary gets reward -1. The actions of the adversary are set as the additive error to the output of the learned environment model.

Figure A-5: Schematic diagram of the Inverted Pendulum task.

D Additional Experimental Results with Known System Dynamics Scenarios

This section reports experimental results on all the evaluation tasks under perturbation types that have not been presented in the main text.

D.1 Control of Perturbed Nonlinear Systems

We run the training process of learning-based algorithms on Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking, and 2-link Pendulum under different perturbation types as shown in Table 1 in the main text until convergence. Control curves under uniform (U) perturbations are shown in Fig. A-6, while control curves under worst-case (W) perturbations learned by the adversary are illustrated in Fig. A-7. We observe that our ARNLC can achieve asymptotic stability under both test scenarios in almost all the tasks, while it reaches the stability the fastest compared to the other baselines. The uniform external force perturbations in the Car Trajectory Tracking task is the only test scenario where our ARNLC performs the worst, as shown in Fig. A-6(k). Though NLC reaches the stability in some tasks, it fails to reach the equilibrium point in Car Trajectory Tracking W, 2-link Pendulum W and U. RARL and robust MPC fail to reach the stability in 2-link Pendulum.

We additionally compute the percentile of negative adversary rewards for controller policies achieved by each algorithm to further evaluate their robustness. We run each policy with 100 different initial system states in each perturbed task, and then sort the cumulative negative adversary reward of each run to obtain the n -th percentile. The results obtained under uniform (U) perturbations are shown in Fig. A-8, while percentile plots under worst-case (W) perturbations learned by the adversary are illustrated in Fig. A-9. In general, control policies that can gain higher rewards at the same percentile perform better. While control policies in a lower percentile have better control performance if they receive the same reward, i.e., they can gain higher rewards with more episodes. We observe that our ARNLC can receive the highest rewards under both test scenarios in all the tasks. RARL sometimes fail to reach the stability in Car Trajectory Tracking, and therefore, RARL sometimes receives extremely low rewards in this task.

Figure A-6: Control curves of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing.

Figure A-7: Control curves of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing.

Figure A-8: Percentile plots of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing.

Figure A-9: Percentile plots of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing.

D.2 Generalization in Perturbation Space

In this subsection, we evaluate the generalization capability of learning-based algorithms in the entire perturbation space generated from other combinations of perturbation types that are not presented in the main text. We observe that ARNLC achieves the best generalization performance among all the combinations of different physical parameters. PNLC generalizes better than NLC in most combinations, while showing worse performance in Figs. A-10(f) and A-10(j).

Figure A-10: Heatmap of averaged cumulative negative adversary's reward for Pendulum, Cart Pole.

D.3 Impact of Control Intervals

We evaluate the impact of different control intervals (0.01s, 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s) to our ARNLC on Pendulum with perturbation types (Length of Pole, Mass of Ball, Friction Coefficient, Acceleration of Gravity) different from the results presented in the main text. The resulting control curves obtained for Pendulum under uniform perturbations are shown in Figs. A-6(a)-A-6(d) and Fig. A-11. And the control curves under perturbation of learned adversary are shown in Figs. A-7(a)-A-7(d) and Fig. A-12. The resulting percentile plots obtained for Pendulum under uniform perturbations are shown in Figs. A-8(a)-A-8(e) and Fig. A-13. And the percentile plots under perturbation of learned adversary are shown in Figs. A-9(a)-A-9(e) and Fig. A-14. The results demonstrate that our ARNLC is robust to different control intervals.

We further evaluate our ARNLC in the continuous-time dynamical system of Pendulum, with the system dynamics given in Eq. (A-6). Here we show that our ARNLC can achieve asymptotic stability faster than NLC in Figs. A-15(a)-A-15(d) and can receive higher rewards in Figs. A-15(e)-A-15(h). The regions of attraction are shown in Figs. A-15(i)-A-15(l), demonstrating that those estimated by our ARNLC are comparable with those estimated by neural Lyapunov Controller. This indicates that we still have the advantage of the larger region of attraction inherited from the original method after incorporating the adversarial training.

Figure A-11: Control curves of Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.

Figure A-12: Control curves of Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.

Figure A-13: Percentile plots of Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.

Figure A-14: Percentile plots of Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.

Figure A-15: Control curves, percentile plots and regions of attraction for pendulum balancing in continuous-time control under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing.

E Additional Experimental Results with Unknown System Dynamics Scenarios

This section reports experimental results for unknown system dynamics. We carry out the same experiments on all the tasks, while assuming that we have no access to the system dynamics. Therefore, we utilize Algorithm 1 in the main text in Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum tasks. The evaluation of robust MPC is excluded here, since it requires to know exactly the system dynamics, which makes it no longer feasible.

E.1 Control of Perturbed Nonlinear Systems

We run the training process of learning-based algorithms on Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking, and 2-link Pendulum utilizing Algorithm 1 in the main text until convergence. Control curves under uniform (U) perturbations are shown in Fig. A-16, while control curves under worst-case (W) perturbations learned by the adversary are illustrated in Fig. A-17. We use the learned adversary in RARL to add perturbations in worst-case testing. This is because for unknown system dynamics, the adversary’s actions are the additive error to the output of the learned environment model, and in testing, we require the perturbations in the true dynamics (e.g., physical parameters or external force). We observe that our ARNLC can achieve asymptotic stability under both test scenarios in almost all the tasks, while it reaches the stability the fastest compared to the other baselines. The learned adversary’s external force perturbations in the Car Trajectory Tracking task is the only test scenario where our ARNLC fails to reach the equilibrium point, as shown in Fig. A-17(i). Though NLC reaches the stability in some tasks, it fails to reach the equilibrium point in Pendulum W, Car Tracking W and 2-link Pendulum U and W, when the perturbation type in testing is the external force. PNLC trained under uniform sampled perturbations outperforms NLC in some tasks (e.g., Pendulum and Cart Pole), but is worse in Car Tracking W and 2-link Pendulum U.

We additionally compute the percentile of rewards for controller policies achieved by each algorithm to further evaluate their robustness. We run each policy with 100 different initial system states in each perturbed task, and then sort the cumulative negative adversary reward of each run to obtain the n -th percentile. The results obtained under uniform (U) perturbations are shown in Fig. A-18, while percentile plots under worst-case (W) perturbations learned by the adversary are illustrated in Fig. A-19. In general, control policies that can gain higher rewards at the same percentile perform better. While control policies in a lower percentile have better control performance if they receive the same reward, i.e., they can gain higher rewards with more episodes. We observe that our ARNLC can receive the highest rewards under both test scenarios in all the tasks. RARL sometimes fails to reach the stability in Car Trajectory Tracking, and therefore, RARL sometimes receives extremely low rewards in this task.

Figure A-16: Control curves of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing.

Figure A-17: Control curves of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing.

Figure A-18: Percentile plots of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing.

Figure A-19: Percentile plots of Pendulum, Cart Pole, Car Trajectory Tracking and 2-link Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing.

E.2 Generalization in Perturbation Space

In this subsection, we evaluate the generalization capability of learning-based algorithms in the entire perturbation space. We observe that ARNLc achieves the best generalization performance under most unknown system dynamics and among all the combinations of different physical parameters. RARL presents the worst performance in all the tasks except for Pendulum.

Figure A-20: Heatmap of averaged controller's reward for Pendulum, Cart Pole and Inverted Pendulum.

E.3 Impact of Control Intervals

We evaluate the impact of different control intervals (0.01s, 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s) to our ARNLC on Pendulum with perturbation types (Length of Pole, Mass of Ball, Friction Coefficient, Acceleration of Gravity) different from the results presented in the main text. The resulting control curves obtained for Pendulum under uniform perturbations are shown in Figs. A-16(a)-A-16(d) and Fig. A-21. And the control curves under perturbation of learned adversary are shown in Figs. A-17(a)-A-17(d) and Fig. A-22. The resulting percentile plots obtained for Pendulum under uniform perturbations are shown in Figs. A-18(a)-A-18(e) and Fig. A-23. And the percentile plots under perturbation of learned adversary are shown in Figs. A-19(a)-A-19(e) and Fig. A-24. The results demonstrate that our ARNLC is robust to different control intervals.

Figure A-21: Control curves of Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.

Figure A-22: Control curves of Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.

Figure A-23: Percentile plots of Pendulum under uniform (U) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.

Figure A-24: Percentile plots of Pendulum under learned adversary's worst-case (W) perturbations in testing with control interval set to 0.1s, 0.005s and 0.001s, respectively.